

Implementation of Common Soft Fixed Point with Intuitionistic Soft Fuzzy Metric Space

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Abstract: In this article, we define compatible mappings of type (K) in intuitionistic fuzzy metric space and prove a general Soft fixed point theorem with an application to self mappings on a full intuitionistic fuzzy metric space. Our conclusion broadens and enhances earlier, related findings in the literature.

Keywords: Intuitionistic fuzzy metric space, weakly compatible, compatible mappings of type (K), Soft set, soft fixed point

Introduction

Functional analysis must include the examination of soft fixed points. Studying frequently occurring soft fixed points of mappings that satisfy contractive type constraints has proven to be a very fruitful field of research. The idea of a fuzzy set was created in 1965 by L.A. Zade[11]. Following that, fuzzy metric spaces were introduced by Kramosil and Michalek [13]. George and Veeramani [1] used continuous t-norms to create the idea of fuzzy metric spaces. In 1986, G. Jungck [5] was the first to put forth the concept of compatible mappings. By G. Jungck, P. P. Murthy, and Y. J. Cho in 1993 [6]. Compatible mappings of type (P) were introduced by M. Kang

[7] and contrasted with compatible mappings of type (A) and compatible mappings. In 1998,. The idea of compatible mappings of type (K) in metric space was recently proposed by Jha et al. [10], who also demonstrated that each compatible mapping of type (K) is independent of the others. A

Preliminaries

Definition 2.1. [12] Any non empty set Y and B is a fuzzy set in Y is a mapping with domain Y and [0,1].

Definition 2.2. [1] A binary operation $\diamond : [0, 1] \times [0, 1] \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is a continuous t-norm if $\diamond$ is satisfying the following conditions:

1. $\diamond$ is commutative and associative;
2. $\diamond$ is continuous;
3. $p \diamond 1 = p$ for all $a \in [0, 1]$;
4. $p \diamond q \leq r \diamond s$ whenever $p \leq r$ and $q \leq s$, and $p, q, r, s \in [0, 1]$.

Definition 2.3. [2] A binary operation $*$: $[0, 1] \times [0, 1] \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is a continuous t-conorm if it satisfies the following conditions:

1. is commutative and associative;
2. $*$ is continuous;
3. $p * 0 = p$ for all $p \in [0, 1]$;
4. $p * q \leq r * s$ whenever $p \leq r$ and $q \leq s$, for each $p, q, r, s \in [0, 1]$.

Definition 2.4. [3] Let $(Y, P, Q, *, \diamond)$ be an intuitionistic fuzzy metric space.

1. A sequence $\{x_n\}$ in Y is called Cauchy sequence if for each $t > 0$ and $P > 0$, $\lim_{\omega \rightarrow \infty} P(y_{\omega+p}, t) = 1$ and $\lim_{\omega \rightarrow \infty} Q(y_{\omega+p}, t) = 0$.
2. A sequence $\{y_n\}$ in Y is convergent to $y \in Y$ if $\lim_{\omega \rightarrow \infty} Q(y_{\omega+p}, t) = 1$ and $\lim_{\omega \rightarrow \infty} Q(y_{\omega+p}, t) = 0$.
3. for each $t > 0$.
4. An intuitionistic fuzzy metric space is said to be complete if every Cauchy sequence is convergent.

Definition 2.5.[10] The self mappings B and R of a fuzzy metric space $(Y, P, *)$ are said to be compatible of type (E) iff $\lim_{\omega \rightarrow \infty} P(BB_{y_{\omega}}, BR_{y_{\omega}}, t) = 1$, $\lim_{\omega \rightarrow \infty} P(BB_{y_{\omega}}, Ry_{\omega}, t) = 1$,

$\lim_{\omega \rightarrow \infty} P(BR_{y_{\omega}}, Ry_{\omega}, t) = 1$ and $\lim_{\omega \rightarrow \infty} P(RR_{y_{\omega}}, RB_{y_{\omega}}, t) = 1, \lim_{\omega \rightarrow \infty} P(RR_{y_{\omega}}, By_{\omega}, t) = 1$,

$\lim_{\omega \rightarrow \infty} P(RR_{y_{\omega}}, By_{\omega}, t) = 1$.

common soft fixed point theorem for compatible mappings of type (K) in intuitionistic fuzzy metric spaces is established in this study with an accompanying illustration. Molodtsov [18] introduced the idea of soft sets as a novel mathematical approach for problem-solving. A parameterized family of subsets of the full set is what Molodtsov[1] refers to as a soft set. Each element of the soft set is thought of as a collection of nearby items, and the soft set is a parameterized family of subsets of the full set. Numerous scholars have been studying the foundations of soft set theory during the past few years. A OR was presented by Maji et al. [19]. They conducted study and discussed the fundamental characteristics of their methods. Pei and Miao [20] examined the connection between information systems and soft sets and redefined the terms intersection and subset of soft sets. [21] with a focus on their fundamental features. Soft matrix theory was introduced by Cagman and Enginoglu [22]

Definition 2.6.[10] The self mappings B and R of a metric space (Y, d) are said to be compatible of type (K) iff $\lim_{\omega \rightarrow \infty} BBy_\omega = Ry$ and $\lim_{\omega \rightarrow \infty} RRY_\omega = By$, whenever $\{y_\omega\}$ is a sequence in Y such that $\lim_{\omega \rightarrow \infty} By_\omega = \lim_{\omega \rightarrow \infty} Ry_\omega = y$ for some y in Y.

Definition 2.7 The self mappings B and R of an intuitionistic fuzzy metric space (Y, P, Q, *, $\diamond$) are said to be compatible of type (K) iff $\lim_{\omega \rightarrow \infty} P(BBy_\omega, Ry, t) = 1$ and $\lim_{\omega \rightarrow \infty} P(RRY_\omega, By, t) = 1$, whenever $\{y_\omega\}$ is a sequence in Y such that $\lim_{\omega \rightarrow \infty} By_\omega = \lim_{\omega \rightarrow \infty} Ry_\omega = y$ for some x in Y and $t > 0$.

Definition 2.10.[18] Let (Y, d) is a metric space and the set (F, B) is a soft set of Y is called null soft set and it is denoted by ϕ . iff for all $\epsilon \in B$, $F(\epsilon) = \phi$. (empty set)

Definition 2.11.[19] Let (Y, d) is a metric space and suppose that the set (F, B) is a soft set over (Y, d) is called absolute soft set. If for all $\epsilon \in B$, $F(\epsilon) = Y$.

Definition 2.12.[20] Let (Y, d) is a metric space and if the difference (F, A) of two soft sets (F, A) and (F, A) over Y is denoted by (F, A)/(F, A) and is defined as

$F(e) = H(e) \setminus G(e)$ for all $e \in A$.

Lemma 2.14. [16] Let (Y, P, Q, *, $\diamond$) be an intuitionistic fuzzy metric space. If there exists a constant $k \in (0, 1)$ such that $P(y_{\omega+2}, y_{\omega+1}, kt) \geq P(y_{\omega+1}, y_\omega, t)$, $Q(y_{\omega+1}, y_{\omega+1}, kt) \leq Q(y_{\omega+1}, y_\omega, t)$ for every $t > 0$ and $n=1, 2, \dots$ then $\{y_\omega\}$ is a Cauchy sequence in Y.

Definition 2.13.[21] For any two soft real numbers

1. $\tilde{p} \leq \tilde{q}$, if $\tilde{p}(e) \leq \tilde{q}(e)$, for all $e \in A$.
2. $\tilde{p} \geq \tilde{q}$ if $\tilde{p}(e) \geq \tilde{q}(e)$, for all $e \in A$.
3. $\tilde{p} < \tilde{q}$ if $\tilde{p}(e) < \tilde{q}(e)$, for all $e \in A$.
4. $\tilde{p} > \tilde{q}$, if $\tilde{p}(e) > \tilde{q}(e)$, for all $e \in A$.

Definition 2.14.[22] The complement of a soft set (P, B) is denoted by $(P, B)^c$ and is defined by $(P, B)^c = (P^c, B)$ where $F: B \rightarrow Q(Y)$ is mapping given by $(\beta) = Y - P(\beta)$, $\forall \beta \in B$.

Definition 2.15.[23] Let R be the set of real numbers and C(R) be the collection of all nonempty Bounded subsets of R and C taken as a set of parameters. Then a mapping

$A: H \rightarrow B(R)$ is said to be a soft real set. It is denoted by (A, H). If specifically (A, H) is a singleton soft set, then identifying (A, H) with the corresponding soft element, it will be said to a soft real number and denoted $\tilde{a}$, betc.

Let 0, 1 are any two soft real numbers where $0(e) = 0, 1(e) = 1$ for all $e \in H$, respectively

Main Results

If the following requirements are met and B, K, L, and T are self mapping on a full intuitionistic soft fuzzy metric space (Y, P, Q, *, $\diamond$),

(i) $C(Y) \subseteq T(Y)$, $K(Y) \subseteq L(Y)$.

There exists $k \in (0, 1)$ such that for every $\tilde{x}, \tilde{y} \in \tilde{Y}$ and $t > 0$,

$P(C\tilde{x}, K\tilde{y}, kt) \geq \min \{P(L\tilde{x}, T\tilde{y}, t), P(C\tilde{x}, L\tilde{x}, t), P(K\tilde{y}, T\tilde{y}, t), P(C\tilde{x}, T\tilde{y}, t), P(C\tilde{x}, K\tilde{y}, t), P(L\tilde{x}, K\tilde{y}, t)\}$,

and $Q(C\tilde{x}, K\tilde{y}, kt) \leq \max \{Q(L\tilde{x}, T\tilde{y}, t), Q(C\tilde{x}, L\tilde{x}, t), Q(K\tilde{y}, T\tilde{y}, t), Q(C\tilde{x}, T\tilde{y}, t), Q(C\tilde{x}, K\tilde{y}, t), Q(L\tilde{x}, K\tilde{y}, t)\}$.

K and T weakly compatible mappings.

Then C, K, L, and T all have a single common soft fixed point in $\tilde{Y}$ if the pair of mappings (C, L) is compatible of type (K) and one of the mappings is continuous.

Theorem 3.1: If the following requirements are met and B, K, L, and T are self mapping on a full intuitionistic soft fuzzy metric space (Y, P, Q, *, $\diamond$),

(i) $C(Y) \subseteq T(Y)$, $K(Y) \subseteq L(Y)$.

There exists $k \in (0, 1)$ such that for every $\tilde{y}, \tilde{z} \in \tilde{Y}$ and $t > 0$,

$P(C_{\tilde{y}}, K_{\tilde{z}}, kt) \geq \min \{P(L_{\tilde{y}}, T_{\tilde{z}}, t), P(C_{\tilde{y}}, L_{\tilde{y}}, t), P(K_{\tilde{z}}, T_{\tilde{z}}, t), P(C_{\tilde{y}}, T_{\tilde{z}}, t), P(C_{\tilde{y}}, K_{\tilde{z}}, t), P(L_{\tilde{y}}, K_{\tilde{z}}, t)\}$,
 and $Q(C_{\tilde{y}}, K_{\tilde{z}}, kt) \leq \max \{Q(L_{\tilde{y}}, T_{\tilde{z}}, t), Q(C_{\tilde{y}}, L_{\tilde{y}}, t), Q(K_{\tilde{z}}, T_{\tilde{z}}, t), Q(C_{\tilde{y}}, T_{\tilde{z}}, t), Q(C_{\tilde{y}}, K_{\tilde{z}}, t), Q(L_{\tilde{y}}, K_{\tilde{z}}, t)\}$.

$$P(C_{\tilde{y}}, K_{\tilde{z}}, kt) \leq \frac{P(L_{\tilde{y}}, K_{\tilde{z}}, t)}{1 + P(L_{\tilde{y}}, K_{\tilde{z}}, t)} \quad \text{and}$$

$$Q(C_{\tilde{y}}, K_{\tilde{z}}, kt) \leq \max\{Q(L_{\tilde{y}}, T_{\tilde{z}}, t), Q(C_{\tilde{y}}, L_{\tilde{z}}, t), Q(K_{\tilde{z}}, T_{\tilde{z}}, t), Q(L_{\tilde{y}}, K_{\tilde{z}}, t)\}$$

$$\frac{1 + Q(C_{\tilde{y}}, T_{\tilde{z}}, t)}{1 + Q(L_{\tilde{y}}, K_{\tilde{z}}, t)}$$

K and T weakly compatible mappings.

Then C, K, L, and T all have a single common soft fixed point in $\tilde{Y}$ if the pair of mappings (C, L) is compatible of type (K) and one of the mappings is continuous

Proof: Suppose $\tilde{y}_0$ be any random point in $\tilde{Y}$, construct a $\{\tilde{z}_n\}$ in $\tilde{Y}$ as a means to $\tilde{z}_{2\omega-1} = T\tilde{y}_{2\omega-1}$

$$= C\tilde{y}_{2\omega-2} \ \& \ \tilde{z}_{2\omega} = L\tilde{y}_{2\omega} = K\tilde{y}_{2\omega+1}, \ \omega = 1, 2, 3, 4 \quad \text{this can be done by (1),}$$

By using contractive condition, we obtain

$$P(\tilde{z}_{2\omega+1}, \tilde{z}_{2\omega+2}, kt) = P(C\tilde{y}_{2\omega}, K\tilde{y}_{2\omega+1}, kt)$$

$$P(\tilde{z}_{2\omega+1}, \tilde{z}_{2\omega+2}, kt) \geq \min\{P(L\tilde{y}_{2\omega}, T\tilde{y}_{2\omega+1}, t), P(C\tilde{y}_{2\omega}, L\tilde{y}_{2\omega+1}, t), P(K\tilde{y}_{2\omega+1}, T\tilde{y}_{2\omega+1}, t), P(L\tilde{y}_{2\omega}, K\tilde{y}_{2\omega+1}, t)\}$$

$$\geq \frac{P(L\tilde{y}_{2\omega}, K\tilde{y}_{2\omega+1}, t)}{1 + P(L\tilde{y}_{2\omega}, K\tilde{y}_{2\omega+1}, t)} \cdot \frac{1 + P(L\tilde{y}_{2\omega}, T\tilde{y}_{2\omega+1}, t)}{1 + P(C\tilde{y}_{2\omega}, T\tilde{y}_{2\omega+1}, t)}$$

$$\geq \min\{P(\tilde{z}_{2\omega}, \tilde{z}_{2\omega+1}, t), P(\tilde{z}_{2\omega+1}, \tilde{z}_{2\omega+1}, t), P(\tilde{z}_{2\omega+1}, z_{2\omega+1}, t), P(\tilde{z}_{2\omega}, \tilde{z}_{2\omega+1}, t)\}$$

$$\frac{P(z_{2\omega+1}, \tilde{z}_{2\omega+1}, t)}{1 + P(z_{2\omega+1}, \tilde{z}_{2\omega+1}, t)} \cdot \frac{1 + P(z_{2\omega+1}, z_{2\omega+1}, t)}{1 + P(\tilde{z}_{2\omega}, z_{2\omega}, t)}$$

$$P(\tilde{z}_{2\omega+1}, \tilde{z}_{2\omega+2}, kt) \geq \min\{P(\tilde{z}_{2\omega}, \tilde{z}_{2\omega+1}, t), P(\tilde{z}_{2\omega+1}, \tilde{z}_{2\omega+1}, t), P(\tilde{z}_{2\omega+1}, z_{2\omega+1}, t), P(\tilde{z}_{2\omega}, \tilde{z}_{2\omega+1}, t)\}$$

$$\frac{P(\tilde{z}_{2\omega}, \tilde{z}_{2\omega+1}, t)}{1 + P(\tilde{z}_{2\omega}, z_{2\omega}, t)}$$

$$P(\tilde{z}_{2\omega+1}, \tilde{z}_{2\omega+2}, kt) \geq \min\{P(\tilde{z}_{2\omega}, \tilde{z}_{2\omega+1}, t), 1, 1, P(\tilde{z}_{2\omega}, \tilde{z}_{2\omega+1}, t), 1, 1\}$$

$$P(\tilde{z}_{2\omega+1}, \tilde{z}_{2\omega+2}, kt) \geq P(\tilde{z}_{2\omega}, \tilde{z}_{2\omega+1}, t)$$

$$\text{Similarly, we have } P(\tilde{z}_{2\omega}, \tilde{z}_{2\omega+1}, t) \geq P(\tilde{z}_{2\omega-1}, \tilde{z}_{2\omega}, t) \quad (1) \text{ So we get } P(\tilde{z}_{2\omega+2}, \tilde{z}_{2\omega+1}, t) \geq P(\tilde{z}_{2\omega+1}, \tilde{z}_{2\omega}, t)$$

Also, we get

$$Q(\tilde{z}_{2\omega+1}, \tilde{z}_{2\omega+2}, kt) = Q(C\tilde{z}_{2\omega}, K\tilde{z}_{2\omega+1}, kt)$$

$$Q(\tilde{z}_{2\omega+1}, \tilde{z}_{2\omega+2}, kt) \leq \max\{Q(L\tilde{y}_{2\omega}, T\tilde{y}_{2\omega+1}, t), Q(C\tilde{y}_{2\omega}, L\tilde{y}_{2\omega+1}, t), Q(K\tilde{y}_{2\omega+1}, T\tilde{y}_{2\omega+1}, t), Q(L\tilde{y}_{2\omega}, K\tilde{y}_{2\omega+1}, t)\}$$

$$\frac{Q(L\tilde{y}_{2\omega}, K\tilde{y}_{2\omega+1}, t)}{1 + Q(L\tilde{y}_{2\omega}, K\tilde{y}_{2\omega+1}, t)}$$

$$\geq \frac{Q(L\tilde{y}_{2\omega}, K\tilde{y}_{2\omega+1}, t)}{1 + Q(C\tilde{y}_{2\omega}, T\tilde{y}_{2\omega+1}, t)} \cdot \frac{1 + Q(L\tilde{y}_{2\omega}, T\tilde{y}_{2\omega+1}, t)}{1 + Q(C\tilde{y}_{2\omega}, T\tilde{y}_{2\omega+1}, t)}$$

$$\leq \max \{Q(\tilde{z}_{2\omega}, \tilde{z}_{2\omega+1}, t), Q(\tilde{z}_{2\omega+1}, \tilde{z}_{2\omega+1}, t), Q(\tilde{z}_{2\omega+1}, z_{2\omega+1}, t), Q(\tilde{z}_{2\omega}, \tilde{z}_{2\omega+1}, t),$$

$$\frac{Q(z_{2\omega+1}, \tilde{z}_{2\omega+1}, t)}{1+Q(\tilde{z}_{2\omega}, \tilde{z}_{2\omega+1}, t)} + \frac{Q(z_{2\omega+1}, \tilde{z}_{2\omega+1}, t)}{1+Q(\tilde{z}_{2\omega}, \tilde{z}_{2\omega+1}, t)} \}$$

$$Q(\tilde{z}_{2\omega+1}, \tilde{z}_{2\omega+2}, kt) \leq \max \{Q(\tilde{z}_{2\omega}, \tilde{z}_{2\omega+1}, t), Q(\tilde{z}_{2\omega+1}, \tilde{z}_{2\omega+1}, t), Q(\tilde{z}_{2\omega+1}, z_{2\omega+1}, t),$$

$$Q(\tilde{z}_{2\omega}, \tilde{z}_{2\omega+1}, t), \frac{Q(z_{2\omega+1}, \tilde{z}_{2\omega+1}, t)}{1+Q(\tilde{z}_{2\omega}, \tilde{z}_{2\omega+1}, t)} \}$$

$$Q(\tilde{z}_{2\omega+1}, \tilde{z}_{2\omega+2}, kt) \leq \{Q(\tilde{z}_{2\omega}, \tilde{z}_{2\omega+1}, t), 0, 0, Q(\tilde{z}_{2\omega}, \tilde{z}_{2\omega+1}, t), 0, 0\} Q(\tilde{z}_{2\omega+1}, \tilde{z}_{2\omega+2}, kt) \leq Q(\tilde{z}_{2\omega}, \tilde{z}_{2\omega+1}, t)$$

Similarly we have

$$Q(\tilde{z}_{2\omega}, \tilde{z}_{2\omega+1}, t) \leq Q(\tilde{z}_{2\omega-1}, \tilde{z}_{2\omega}, t) \quad (2) \text{ So we get } Q(\tilde{z}_{2\omega+2}, \tilde{z}_{2\omega+1}, t) \leq Q(\tilde{z}_{2\omega+1}, \tilde{z}_{2\omega}, t)$$

From (1),(2) and (2.13), We comprehend that $\{z\}$ is a Cauchy sequence in Y .

But $(Y, \tilde{P}, \tilde{Q}, *, \diamond)$ is complete, So there are a soft point $\tilde{z}$ in $\tilde{Y}$. Such that $\{\tilde{z}_\omega\} \rightarrow \tilde{q}$. Also we have $\{\tilde{C}\tilde{y}_{2\omega-2}\}, \{\tilde{T}\tilde{y}_{2\omega-1}\}, \{\tilde{L}\tilde{y}_{2\omega}\}, \{\tilde{K}\tilde{y}_{2\omega-1}\} \rightarrow \tilde{q}$.

Since (C, L) is compatible of type (K) and one of the mapping is continuous. So using (2.15), We obtain $C\tilde{q} = L\tilde{q}$.

(3)

Since $C(\tilde{Y}) \subseteq T(\tilde{Y})$, Then one can find a point $\tilde{v}$ in $\tilde{Y}$, as a means to $C\tilde{q} = T\tilde{v}$.

Now by contractive condition, we obtain

$$P(C\tilde{q}, K\tilde{v}, kt) \geq \min \{P(L\tilde{q}, T\tilde{v}, t), P(C\tilde{q}, L\tilde{v}, t), P(K\tilde{v}, T\tilde{v}, t), \frac{P(L\tilde{q}, K\tilde{v}, t)}{1+(L\tilde{q}, \tilde{v}, t)}\}$$

$$P(C\tilde{q}, K\tilde{v}, t), \frac{P(C\tilde{q}, T\tilde{v}, t)}{1+(C\tilde{q}, \tilde{v}, t)} \}$$

$$= \min \{P(C\tilde{q}, C\tilde{q}, t), P(C\tilde{q}, C\tilde{q}, t), P(K\tilde{v}, C\tilde{q}, t), \frac{P(C\tilde{q}, K\tilde{v}, t)}{1+(C\tilde{q}, \tilde{v}, t)}\}$$

$$P(C\tilde{q}, C\tilde{q}, t), \frac{P(C\tilde{q}, K\tilde{v}, t)}{1+(C\tilde{q}, \tilde{v}, t)} \}$$

$$= \min \{P(C\tilde{q}, C\tilde{q}, t), P(C\tilde{q}, C\tilde{q}, t), P(K\tilde{v}, C\tilde{q}, t), P(K\tilde{v}, C\tilde{q}, t), P(C\tilde{q}, C\tilde{q}, t), P(K\tilde{v}, C\tilde{q}, t)\}$$

$$P(C\tilde{q}, K\tilde{v}, kt) \geq P(C\tilde{q}, K\tilde{v}, t) \quad (4)$$

Also, we obtain

$$Q(C\tilde{q}, K\tilde{v}, kt) \leq \max \{Q(L\tilde{q}, T\tilde{v}, t), Q(C\tilde{q}, L\tilde{v}, t), Q(K\tilde{v}, T\tilde{v}, t), \frac{Q(L\tilde{q}, K\tilde{v}, t)}{1+Q(L\tilde{q}, \tilde{v}, t)}\}$$

$$Q(C\tilde{q}, K\tilde{v}, t), \frac{Q(C\tilde{q}, T\tilde{v}, t)}{1+Q(C\tilde{q}, \tilde{v}, t)} \}$$

$$= \max \{Q(C\tilde{q}, C\tilde{q}, t), Q(C\tilde{q}, C\tilde{q}, t), Q(K\tilde{v}, C\tilde{q}, t), \frac{Q(C\tilde{q}, K\tilde{v}, t)}{1+Q(C\tilde{q}, \tilde{v}, t)}\}$$

$$Q(C\tilde{q}, C\tilde{q}, t), \frac{Q(C\tilde{q}, K\tilde{v}, t)}{1+Q(C\tilde{q}, \tilde{v}, t)} \}$$

$$= \max \{ Q(C\tilde{q}, C\tilde{q}, t), Q(C\tilde{q}, C\tilde{q}, t), Q(K\tilde{v}, C\tilde{q}, t), Q(K\tilde{v}, C\tilde{q}, t), Q(C\tilde{q}, C\tilde{q}, t), Q(K\tilde{v}, C\tilde{q}, t) \}$$

$$Q(C\tilde{q}, K\tilde{v}, kt) \leq Q(C\tilde{q}, K\tilde{v}, t) \quad (5)$$

Now from (4) and (5) and Lemma (2.14), We obtain $C\tilde{q} = K\tilde{v}$

$$\text{Thus we obtain } C\tilde{q} = L\tilde{q} = K\tilde{q} = T\tilde{q} \quad (6)$$

To prove $R\tilde{q} = \tilde{q}$

$$P(C\tilde{q}, Kz_{2\omega+1}, kt) \geq \min \{ P(L\tilde{q}, Tz_{2\omega+1}, t), P(C\tilde{q}, Lz_{2\omega+1}, t), P(Kz_{2\omega+1}, Tz_{2\omega+1}, t) \},$$

$$\frac{P(L\tilde{q}, Tz_{2\omega+1}, t)}{1 + P(L\tilde{q}, Tz_{2\omega+1}, t)}$$

$$, P(C\tilde{q}, Kz_{2\omega+1}, t)$$

$$,$$

$$, t), \frac{P(C\tilde{q}, Tz_{2\omega+1}, t)}{1 + P(C\tilde{q}, Tz_{2\omega+1}, t)} \}$$

$$1 + P(C\tilde{q}, Tz_{2\omega+1}, t)$$

let as $n \rightarrow \infty$, we obtain

$$P(C\tilde{q}, \tilde{q}, kt) \geq \min \{ P(L\tilde{q}, \tilde{q}, t), P(C\tilde{q}, \tilde{q}, t), P(\tilde{q}, \tilde{q}, t), \frac{P(L\tilde{q}, \tilde{q}, t)}{1 + P(L\tilde{q}, \tilde{q}, t)} \}$$

$$, P(C\tilde{q}, \tilde{q}, t), \frac{P(C\tilde{q}, \tilde{q}, t)}{1 + P(C\tilde{q}, \tilde{q}, t)} \}$$

$$1 + P(C\tilde{q}, \tilde{q}, t)$$

$$P(C\tilde{q}, \tilde{q}, kt) = \min \{ P(L\tilde{q}, \tilde{q}, t), P(C\tilde{q}, \tilde{q}, t), 1, \frac{P(C\tilde{q}, \tilde{q}, t)}{1 + P(C\tilde{q}, \tilde{q}, t)} \}$$

$$1 + P(C\tilde{q}, \tilde{q}, t)$$

$$, P(C\tilde{q}, \tilde{q}, t), \frac{P(C\tilde{q}, \tilde{q}, t)}{1 + P(C\tilde{q}, \tilde{q}, t)} \}$$

$$1 + P(C\tilde{q}, \tilde{q}, t)$$

$$P(C\tilde{q}, \tilde{q}, kt) = \min \{ P(C\tilde{q}, \tilde{q}, t), P(C\tilde{q}, \tilde{q}, t), 1, \frac{P(C\tilde{q}, \tilde{q}, t)}{1 + P(C\tilde{q}, \tilde{q}, t)} \}$$

$$1 + P(C\tilde{q}, \tilde{q}, t)$$

$$, P(C\tilde{q}, \tilde{q}, t), \frac{P(C\tilde{q}, \tilde{q}, t)}{1 + P(C\tilde{q}, \tilde{q}, t)} \}$$

$$1 + P(C\tilde{q}, \tilde{q}, t)$$

$$P(C\tilde{q}, \tilde{q}, kt) = \min \{ P(C\tilde{q}, \tilde{q}, t), P(C\tilde{q}, \tilde{q}, t), 1, 1, P(C\tilde{q}, \tilde{q}, t), 1 \}$$

$$P(C\tilde{q}, \tilde{q}, kt) \geq P(C\tilde{q}, \tilde{q}, t) \quad (7)$$

$$Q(C\tilde{q}, Kz_{2\omega+1}, kt) \leq \max \{ Q(L\tilde{q}, Tz_{2\omega+1}, t), Q(C\tilde{q}, Lz_{2\omega+1}, t), Q(Kz_{2\omega+1}, Tz_{2\omega+1}, t) \},$$

$$\frac{Q(L\tilde{q}, Tz_{2\omega+1}, t)}{1 + Q(L\tilde{q}, Tz_{2\omega+1}, t)}, Q(C\tilde{q}, Kz_{2\omega+1}, t)$$

$$1 + Q(L\tilde{q}, Tz_{2\omega+1}, t)$$

let as $n \rightarrow \infty$, we obtain

$$2\omega+1$$

$$, t), \frac{Q(C\tilde{q}, Tz_{2\omega+1}, t)}{1 + Q(C\tilde{q}, Tz_{2\omega+1}, t)} \}$$

$$1 + Q(C\tilde{q}, Tz_{2\omega+1}, t)$$

$$Q(C\tilde{q}, \tilde{q}, kt) \leq \max \{ Q(L\tilde{q}, \tilde{q}, t), Q(C\tilde{q}, \tilde{q}, t), Q(\tilde{q}, \tilde{q}, t), \frac{Q(L\tilde{q}, \tilde{q}, t)}{1 + Q(L\tilde{q}, \tilde{q}, t)} \}$$

$$1 + Q(L\tilde{q}, \tilde{q}, t)$$

$$, Q(C\tilde{q}, \tilde{q}, t), \frac{Q(C\tilde{q}, \tilde{q}, t)}{1 + Q(C\tilde{q}, \tilde{q}, t)} \}$$

$$1 + Q(C\tilde{q}, \tilde{q}, t)$$

$$Q(C\tilde{q}, \tilde{q}, kt) = \max \left\{ \frac{Q(L\tilde{q}, \tilde{q}, t)}{1+Q(C\tilde{q}, \tilde{q}, t)}, \frac{Q(C\tilde{q}, \tilde{q}, t)}{1+Q(C\tilde{q}, \tilde{q}, t)}, 0, \frac{Q(C\tilde{q}, \tilde{q}, t)}{1+Q(C\tilde{q}, \tilde{q}, t)}, Q(C\tilde{q}, \tilde{q}, t) \right\}$$

$$Q(C\tilde{q}, \tilde{q}, kt) = \max \left\{ Q(C\tilde{q}, \tilde{q}, t), Q(C\tilde{q}, \tilde{q}, t), 0, \frac{Q(C\tilde{q}, \tilde{q}, t)}{1+Q(C\tilde{q}, \tilde{q}, t)}, Q(C\tilde{q}, \tilde{q}, t), Q(C\tilde{q}, \tilde{q}, t) \right\}$$

$$1+Q(C\tilde{q}, \tilde{q}, t) \\
Q(C\tilde{q}, \tilde{q}, kt) = \max \left\{ Q(C\tilde{q}, \tilde{q}, t), Q(C\tilde{q}, \tilde{q}, t), 0, 0, Q(C\tilde{q}, \tilde{q}, t), 0 \right\} \\
1+Q(C\tilde{q}, \tilde{q}, t)$$

$$Q(C\tilde{q}, \tilde{q}, kt) \leq \max Q(C\tilde{q}, \tilde{q}, t) \quad (8)$$

Now from (7) and (8) & lemma 2.14, we obtain

$$C\tilde{q} = \tilde{q}$$

That being the case, we obtain $C\tilde{q} = L\tilde{q} = \tilde{q}$ So $\tilde{q}$ is a common soft point of C and L. (9)

$$\text{As well we obtain } K\tilde{v} = T\tilde{v} = \tilde{q} \quad (10)$$

Since K and T are weakly compatible, we have $T K\tilde{v} = K T\tilde{v}$.

$$\text{So from (6), we obtain } T\tilde{q} = K\tilde{q} \text{ Again, we obtain} \quad (11)$$

$$P(C\tilde{z}, K\tilde{q}, kt) \geq \min \left\{ \frac{P(L\tilde{z}, T\tilde{q}, t)}{1+P(C\tilde{z}, T\tilde{q}, t)}, \frac{P(C\tilde{z}, T\tilde{q}, t)}{1+P(C\tilde{z}, T\tilde{q}, t)} \right\}$$

$$P(C\tilde{z}, L\tilde{q}, t), \frac{P(C\tilde{z}, T\tilde{q}, t)}{1+P(C\tilde{z}, T\tilde{q}, t)} \}$$

Taking limit $n \rightarrow \infty$, We have

$$P(\tilde{q}, K\tilde{q}, kt) \geq \min \left\{ P(\tilde{q}, T\tilde{q}, t), P(\tilde{q}, L\tilde{q}, t), P(K\tilde{q}, T\tilde{q}, t), \frac{P(\tilde{q}, T\tilde{q}, t)}{1+P(\tilde{q}, T\tilde{q}, t)} \right\}$$

$$P(\tilde{q}, K\tilde{q}, kt) \geq \min \left\{ P(\tilde{q}, T\tilde{q}, t), P(\tilde{q}, T\tilde{q}, t), P(T\tilde{q}, T\tilde{q}, t), \frac{P(\tilde{q}, T\tilde{q}, t)}{1+P(\tilde{q}, T\tilde{q}, t)} \right\}$$

$$P(T\tilde{q}, T\tilde{q}, t), \frac{P(\tilde{q}, T\tilde{q}, t)}{1+P(\tilde{q}, T\tilde{q}, t)} \}$$

$$1+P(\tilde{q}, T\tilde{q}, t) \quad 1+P(\tilde{q}, T\tilde{q}, t)$$

$$P(\tilde{q}, K\tilde{q}, kt) \geq \min \left\{ P(\tilde{q}, T\tilde{q}, t), P(\tilde{q}, T\tilde{q}, t), 1, P(\tilde{q}, T\tilde{q}, t), 1, P(\tilde{q}, T\tilde{q}, t) \right\}$$

$$P(\tilde{q}, K\tilde{q}, kt) \geq P(\tilde{q}, T\tilde{q}, t) \quad (12)$$

As well, we obtain

$$Q(C\tilde{z}) Q(C\tilde{z})$$

$2\omega-2$

$2\omega-2$

$$, K\tilde{q}, kt) \leq \max \{ Q(L\tilde{z}, L\tilde{q}, t), \frac{Q(C\tilde{z}2\omega-2, T\tilde{q}, t)}{1+Q(C\tilde{z}2\omega-2, T\tilde{q}, t)} \}$$

$$, T\tilde{q}, t), Q(C\tilde{z}2\omega-2, T\tilde{q}, t), \frac{Q(C\tilde{z}2\omega-2, T\tilde{q}, t)}{1+Q(C\tilde{z}2\omega-2, T\tilde{q}, t)} \}$$

Taking limit $n \rightarrow \infty$, We have

$$Q(\tilde{q}, K\tilde{q}, kt) \leq \max \{ Q(\tilde{q}, T\tilde{q}, t), P(\tilde{q}, L\tilde{q}, t), Q(K\tilde{q}, T\tilde{q}, t), \frac{Q(\tilde{q}, T\tilde{q}, t)}{1+Q(\tilde{q}, T\tilde{q}, t)} \}$$

$$Q(\tilde{q}, K\tilde{q}, kt) \leq \max \{ Q(\tilde{q}, T\tilde{q}, t), Q(\tilde{q}, T\tilde{q}, t), Q(T\tilde{q}, T\tilde{q}, t), \frac{Q(\tilde{q}, T\tilde{q}, t)}{1+Q(\tilde{q}, T\tilde{q}, t)} \}$$

$$, Q(T\tilde{q}, T\tilde{q}, t), \frac{Q(\tilde{q}, T\tilde{q}, t)}{1+Q(\tilde{q}, T\tilde{q}, t)} \}$$

$$Q(\tilde{q}, K\tilde{q}, kt) \leq \max \{ Q(\tilde{q}, T\tilde{q}, t), Q(\tilde{q}, T\tilde{q}, t), 1, Q(\tilde{q}, T\tilde{q}, t), 1, Q(\tilde{q}, T\tilde{q}, t) \}$$

$$Q(\tilde{q}, K\tilde{q}, kt) \leq Q(\tilde{q}, T\tilde{q}, t) \quad (13)$$

Now from (12) and (13) and Lemma(2.14)

$$\text{Since we have } T\tilde{q} = K\tilde{q} = \tilde{q} \quad (14)$$

That being the case, we obtain $\tilde{q}$ is a ordinary soft fixed point of C,K,L and T. For Uniqueness

Suppose $\tilde{r}$ be the another ordinary soft fixed point then $C\tilde{r} = L\tilde{r} = K\tilde{r} \quad R\tilde{r} = \tilde{r}$

$$P(C\tilde{q}, \tilde{K}\tilde{r}, kt) \geq \min \{ P((L\tilde{q}, T\tilde{r}, t), P(C\tilde{q}, L\tilde{r}, t), P(\tilde{K}\tilde{r}, T\tilde{r}, t), \frac{P(C\tilde{q}, T\tilde{r}, t)}{1+P(C\tilde{q}, T\tilde{r}, t)} \}$$

$$P(C\tilde{q}, \tilde{K}\tilde{r}, kt) \geq \min \{ P((C\tilde{q}, K\tilde{r}, t), P(C\tilde{q}, \tilde{C}\tilde{r}, t), P(\tilde{K}\tilde{r}, K\tilde{r}, t), \frac{P(C\tilde{q}, K\tilde{r}, t)}{1+P(C\tilde{q}, K\tilde{r}, t)} \}$$

$$P(C\tilde{q}, \tilde{K}\tilde{r}, kt) = \min \{ P((C\tilde{q}, \tilde{K}\tilde{r}, t), P(C\tilde{q}, C\tilde{r}, t), 1, P(C\tilde{q}, K\tilde{r}, t), P(C\tilde{q}, \tilde{K}\tilde{r}, t), P(C\tilde{q}, K\tilde{r}, t) \}$$

$$(C\tilde{q}, \tilde{K}\tilde{r}, kt) \geq P((C\tilde{q}, \tilde{K}\tilde{r}, t) \quad (15)$$

As well we obtain

$$Q(C\tilde{q}, K\tilde{r}, kt) \leq \max \{ Q((L\tilde{q}, T\tilde{r}, t), Q(C\tilde{q}, L\tilde{r}, t), Q(K\tilde{r}, T\tilde{r}, t), \frac{Q(C\tilde{q}, T\tilde{r}, t)}{1+Q(C\tilde{q}, T\tilde{r}, t)} \}$$

$$Q(C\tilde{q}, K\tilde{r}, kt) \leq \max \{ Q((C\tilde{q}, K\tilde{r}, t), Q(C\tilde{q}, \tilde{C}\tilde{r}, t), Q(K\tilde{r}, \tilde{K}\tilde{r}, t), \frac{Q(C\tilde{q}, K\tilde{r}, t)}{1+Q(C\tilde{q}, K\tilde{r}, t)} \}$$

$$Q(C\tilde{q}, K\tilde{r}, t), \quad Q(C\tilde{q}, K\tilde{r}, t)$$

$$1+ Q(L\tilde{q}, K\tilde{r}, t)$$

$$Q(C\tilde{q}, K\tilde{r}, kt) \leq \max \{ Q((C\tilde{q}, K\tilde{r}, t), Q(C\tilde{q}, C\tilde{r}, t), 0, Q(C\tilde{q}, K\tilde{r}, t), Q(C\tilde{q}, K\tilde{r}, t), Q(C\tilde{q}, K\tilde{r}, t) \}$$

$$Q(C\tilde{q}, K\tilde{r}, kt) \leq Q((C\tilde{q}, K\tilde{r}, t) \quad (16)$$

From (15),(16) and Lemma(2.14)

We obtain $C\tilde{q} = K\tilde{q}$, This implies $C\tilde{q} = C\tilde{r}$,and $\tilde{q}$ is a unique soft fixed point.

Remarks: Our result is also true for the pair of mappings (A, S) is compatible of type (E) in place of compatible mapping of type (K). Our result extends and generalizes the results of M. Verma and R.S. Chandel [13], Jha *et al.*[11] Manandhar *et al.* and improve the result of Manandhar *et al.* [10]. Also, our result improves other similar results in literature.

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